

cement tanks, ponds, or other controlled environments.

In recent surveys, the snail and its egg masses (Fig. 1a) were found in abundance in the *Azolla* propagation ponds of the U.P. College of Agriculture at Los Baños (Fig. 1b) and in adjoining irrigated ricefields on the IRRI experimental farm. The snail feeds voraciously on *Azolla*. Adults measuring 22-26 mm can consume up to 15 g of *Azolla* fronds in 12-24 h.

The snail feeds also on other succulent aquatic vegetation, such as newly transplanted rice. It attacks the base of rice seedlings and then devours aerial parts. A large snail can consume a blade of rice in 3-5 min (Fig. 1c). The snail is most active at dusk, night, and dawn.

Damage is most severe in low-lying portions of newly transplanted ricefields. Severely damaged plots are characterized by missing seedlings and floating, cut leaves (Fig. 1d). Damage can reach 10-20%. In a freshly transplanted 0.1-ha ricefield on the IRRI farm where damage was observed, three 3-gallon pails of golden apple snails were collected.

Females start laying eggs at 75-90 d, preferably on substrates protruding above the water surface (rice hills, weeds, rat fence walls, and bamboo stakes). A single gravid female can lay 25-320 bright pink eggs per week. Eggs hatch in 8-15 d, depending upon temperature.

Newly hatched snail larvae about 2 mm in diameter readily disperse

1. Golden apple snail: a) females and their egg masses on rice plants; b) clusters of egg masses on bamboo stakes in an *Azolla* propagation pond; c) full-grown snail grazing on a rice seedling; d) missing seedlings due to feeding by full-grown snails.

through irrigation water to other ricefields. Young snails feed on algae. Older snails have a horny tongue or radula with rows upon rows of sharp teeth (Fig. 2). The snails are more active and grow faster during warmer months, but mortality is high under hot temperatures.

The golden apple snail can be controlled with organotin molluscicides. However, these chemicals are also toxic to aquatic animals such as fish and tadpoles. Manual collection of snail egg masses can alleviate the problem in ricefields. □

2. Radular tooth pattern of the golden apple snail.

Irrigation Water Management

The effect of supplementary irrigation on rice yield in Bangladesh

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In Bangladesh, rice is grown in aus (summer), aman (autumn), and boro (winter). Although aus and aman rice cover 89% of the total cropped area and yield 84% of the total rice output, they are still grown as rainfed crops. Uncertain rainfall during transplanting

and critical growth periods means crop losses, even though 80% of the mean annual rainfall in the country (1,400 mm in the northwest to over 5,000 mm in the northeast) occurs during aus and aman.

We studied the amount of

supplementary irrigation needed, its effect on yield, and the risks associated with rainfed aus and aman rice cultivation on the farm of the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, in 1980-81. The three treatments were 1) rainfed, 2) rainfed with supplementary irrigation to keep the plots saturated, and 3) rainfed with supplementary irrigation to keep the plots under 25-50 mm standing water. The water balance method was used to determine the crop water requirement, with provisions for measuring rainfall, evaporation, and seepage and percolation.

Treatment 3 had yields 8-71% higher than in treatment 1 during aus and 71% higher during aman. Rainfall was 842 mm during aus and 783 mm during aman. Supplementary irrigation was required because of erratic distribution. For treatment 3, 69 mm supplementary irrigation was required in aus and 573 mm in aman. For treatment 2, a 57% higher yield over treatment 1 during aman required only 15 mm supplementary irrigation. Crop water requirements at field level

Supplementary irrigation required (SIR) during aus and aman seasons at rainfall probabilities of 25, 50, and 75%. BIRRI, Bangladesh. 1980-81.

were calculated as 643 mm for aus and 893 mm for aman.

Probability analysis projected that aus rice would require supplementary irrigation in 1 out of 4 yr and aman rice 3 out of 4 yr. The amount of

supplementary irrigation required would vary 0-69 mm with rainfall probabilities of 50-75% for aus and 67-309 mm with rainfall probabilities of 25-75% for aman (see figure). □

Irrigation management for lowland rice under water constraint

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A trial on irrigation practices used IR50 rice on clay loam soil at TNAU during 1985 kharif and 1986 summer. Kharif treatments were 1) continuous 5-cm submergence, 2) saturation to 5-cm submergence, 3) field capacity to 5-cm submergence, 4) a turn system of two 7-cm irrigations at 3- and 4-d intervals in 1 wk, with no irrigation the alternate week, and 5) continuous 5-cm submergence to 30 d after transplanting (DT) and thereafter no irrigation for 4 d, followed by 1 wk continuous submergence. In summer, field capacity submergence was

Water management effects on yield in Tamil Nadu, 1985-86.^a

Treatment	Kharif			Summer		
	Water consumed (mm)	Yield (t/ha)	WUE (kg/ha mm)	Water consumed (mm)	Yield (t/ha)	WUE (kg/ha mm)
1	1639	5.30	3.2	1651	5.18	3.1
2	971	5.19	5.8	1013	5.04	5.0
3	723	4.18	6.4	1430	5.48	3.8
4	917	4.58	6.0	960	4.83	5.0
5	1463	4.98	4.1	1387	5.24	3.8
CD at 5%	—	0.57	—	—	0.46	—

^aWUE = water use efficiency.

replaced by a partial turn system — 4 d no irrigation followed by 1 wk continuous 5-cm submergence up to 30 DT — and then continuous submergence.

Saturation to 5-cm submergence

saved about 40% of the water needed for continuous submergence without significantly affecting yield (see table). Under the turn system, yields were 14% less in kharif and 7% less in summer. □